

Role of color transformation during Fenton's oxidation of phenolic waste water in a large scale continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR)

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Abstract : Fenton's reagent was used to degrade toxic and refractory aromatic compound phenol in synthetic waste water in a large scale CSTR. Twenty experiments were carried out and optimum condition was achieved for various process parameters viz. pH, catalyst (Fe^{2+}) concentration, phenol : H_2O_2 , feeding mode of oxidant, TOC removal etc. pH = 3.0-3.5, Fe^{2+} (catalyst) = 24 mg/L, phenol : H_2O_2 = 1 : 12 (w/v), feeding mode : initial phenol concentration = 100 mg/L and maximum TOC removal = 36.23%. IR spectra of the final solution were taken to investigate the low mineralization efficiency which is due to formation of aliphatic carboxylic acids. Fenton process was modeled into pseudo-first order kinetics, where overall rate constant is found to be = $1.121 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Color transformation was studied in details with respect to various process parameters to establish it as a physical indicator for conversion status of the contaminant.

Keywords : Phenol degradation, large scale continuous stirred tank reactor, color transformation, Fenton's oxidation, TOC removal.

Introduction

Environmental pollution on a global scale has been drawn attention to the vital need for an environmentally clean and friendly chemical process. Advanced oxidation process (AOP) is one of them. Among various possible AOP, Fenton reaction is widely studied and it is very useful for degradation of hazardous and refractory molecule like phenol¹. AOP's are based on formation of hydroxyl anion (OH^\bullet), a strong oxidant ($E_0 = 2.80 \text{ V}$) resulting from several reactions such as synergistic effect of two oxidant. Using Fenton reaction, toxic and nonbiodegradable ring structure can be made less toxic and more amenable to biological oxidation. The reaction is exothermic and associated with foaming and gas production. Generally biological oxidation is a common method to degrade phenol waste water but toxicity of phenol can disrupt activated sludge process². Hence chemical oxidation of dissolved organics in industrial effluents is an alternative technology that can be applied to broad spectrum of organic compounds including phenol. A criti-

cal review of literature reveals that numerous works are carried out on degradation of phenol³, kinetics of phenol oxidation⁴, role of different anions on phenol oxidation by Fenton reaction⁵ role and comparison of various AOP's on phenolic waste water degradation⁶, use of TiO_2 and ZnO for enhancing oxidation²¹. But very little emphasis was given on color generation during Fenton's oxidation with respect to various process parameters in a large scale reactor. Although chemical characteristic of the final water was not studied in detail, an attempt was made to understand the fate of the phenol conversion by liquid phase IR spectroscopy. Color generation has a strong correlation with TOC removal and contaminant degradation which is supported by established mechanism of phenol oxidation⁷. To investigate catalyst regeneration with initial phenol concentration AAS analysis was performed. As the quantum of waste water discharge by various industries like petroleum refinery is huge so there is a strong requirement for carrying out Fenton's oxidation in a large scale CSTR. Although the production of colored waste water

makes it difficult to implement this oxidation treatment but the color shown by the water during oxidation treatment could be used as overall indicator of their oxidation state⁷. In the light of the above facts, present study is an attempt to highlight correlation between color formation and transformation of phenolic waste water with optimization of process parameters.

Chemicals :

Phenol was obtained from Merck, India. AR quality hydrogen peroxide was purchased from Merck, India and stored in refrigerator. Others chemicals like ferrous ammonium sulphate, 4-amino antipyrine, hydrochloric acid, potassium ferrocyanide $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ was purchased from Merck, India.

Instruments :

Gradual conversion of phenol was monitored by using a Shimadzu (UV-160A) spectrophotometer. Total organic carbon was measured by Shimadzu TOC analyzer. The pH of the solutions for different run was measured by EI Digital pH meter. The Shimadzu IR spectrophotometer was used for IR study. Total iron is analyzed by Varian GTA 120, AA420 AAS.

Experimental

The reactions were carried out in a batch reactor having connected with a pump for proper circulation. The reactor is suitable for treating 100 liter of waste water. Different concentration of waste water was prepared synthetically by mixing requisite amount of phenol to the reactor. Total reaction time was 30 min for all the experimental runs. Experimental runs were performed considering various process parameters like pH, phenol-hydrogen peroxide ratio, catalyst concentration, catalyst variation during reaction, initial phenol concentration and feeding mode to keep parity with transformation of phenol. Selected experiments were reanalyzed to find out the reproducibility which is nearly $\pm 3\%$. Except this, sample was withdrawn time to time for monitoring TOC conversion. Residual iron in the solution is measured with AAS at specific time intervals. Color change during the reaction was measured by its absorbance value at different time interval at 450 nm which was supported by some authors⁸. Keeping all the parameters at its optimum level, the final solution of phenol conversion (after 30 min reaction segment) was extracted in chloroform and send for IR analysis. Twelve peaks were observed by scanning

Fig. 1. Schematic of reaction set up.

from 348.088 cm^{-1} to 7800 cm^{-1} from which the broad peak was observed at 3357.41 cm^{-1} .

Results and discussion

Changes in solution color : Initially, the solution was colorless, but immediately after the addition of the hydrogen peroxide, a yellow coloration appeared. After 5 min, the color changed through orange to brown to black. After 15 min, the color began to disappear and the solution finally became very light shade of orange-yellow after 30 min. This fact is supported by Bremner *et al.*

Color transformation has a strong correlation with the mechanism provided by John Potter *et al.*⁹ and Fed Ericomijangos¹⁰. Dark color formation after 15–20 min of the reaction is due to generation of ferric catecholate type complex or 1 : 1 type quinhydrone type complex. After 30 min this compounds broken to form *cis*, *cis*-muconic acid and other aliphatic counterparts which is reflected in the absorbance data.

Table 1

Time interval (min)	Absorbance
1.0	0.052
2.5	0.083
3.10	0.103
4.15	0.217
6.20	0.331
7.25	0.178
8.30	0.138
9.35	0.125
10.40	0.111
11.45	0.09

The following mechanism is consulted throughout the study which is proposed by John Potter *et al.*⁹ and Fed Ericomijangos¹⁰ (Fig. 2).

Effect of initial pH on reaction rate and the solution :

The experiments are carried at different pH values starting from 2.7 to 7.0 keeping other parameter constant. Alkaline range is not selected as mechanism⁹ clearly shows that Fenton's reaction mostly occurred at acidic pH. It was found from experiment that initial pH has a significant influence on color generation and subsequent phenol conversion. Formation of dark color has direct relationship with phenol conversion which reaches optimum value at pH 3.0–3.5.

Fig. 2. Proposed reaction mechanism for phenol conversion.

OH^- is trapped at low pH condition which augments production of OH^\bullet , the most effective free radical for oxidation. It leads to formation of other oxygenated intermediates¹¹. At low pH formation of ferric complexes also increases. As the reaction proceeds, the pH declines, first at the point where the ferrous sulfate was added, and then a more pronounced decline at the point where hydrogen peroxide was added. This occurs partly due to the fragmentation of organic material into organic acids. The gradual decrease in pH value reaches its maximum for an initial phenol concentration of 500 mg/L, which is shown in Fig. 3. This may be illustrated by the fact that with increasing phenol concentration, aliphatic carboxylic acid produced through degradation also increases, which explains the trend.

Effect of phenol and oxidant ratio :

From different experimental ratios 1 : 6, 1 : 9, 1 : 12 performed at room temperature. Initial concentration of phenol was fixed at 100 ppm and catalyst concentration was 0.42 mM. Conversion efficiency increases with

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on phenol conversion.

Fig. 3A. Change of pH during Fenton's oxidation.

increasing oxidant concentration. Following reaction clearly depicts that at higher hydrogen peroxide concentration higher amount of hydroxyl radicals are generated.

Again excess H_2O_2 can react with Fe^{3+} . Hence by repeating the different batch reactions the optimum condi-

tion was achieved at 1 : 12 (Fig. 4). It also support the color generation. That deep color formation from yellow to dark brown enhances at this temperature which ensure the rupture of aromatic ring and formation of charge transfer complexes.

Effect of initial Fe^{2+} concentration :

The initial Fe^{2+} concentration showed a significant influence on the phenol degradation and consequent color transformation. This two factors posses a strong resem-

Fig. 4. Effect of phenol-oxidant ratio on phenol conversion.

blance with proposed mechanism. By performing various batch experiments with optimum pH, phenol-oxidant ratio and initial phenol concentration at 100 mg/L the optimum catalyst concentration was found to be 0.42 mM it is shown in Fig. 5.

At this concentration maximum Fe^{2+} is consumed which is due to the following reaction :

At higher relative abundance of Fe^{3+} ions ferric catecholate complex is generated more quickly which makes the solution darker. It is an indicator of destruction of aromatic moiety.

Variation of catalyst concentration with initial phenol concentration :

From the proposed mechanism when iron concentration in the solution is increased the rate of formation of colored compounds is also enhanced¹⁰. This behavior may be explained by considering that iron reacts with hydrogen peroxide to produce free radicals and ferric ions, but these ions are extremely labile and hence therefore, can react with catechol present in synthetic waste water to form metal complexes. These chelated complexes having iron are colored species that persist throughout the pro-

cess and generate more dense color in the oxidized water. In our study the AAS analysis revealed the fact that with progress of the reaction iron concentration decreases which is due to the complex formation already depicted before. After first phase of the reaction the concentration becomes almost stagnant and then decreases as iron complexes are destroyed to form aliphatic acids. Fig. 5A will illustrate the trend. Liberated iron is present in ferrous state may be oxidized and can form iron containing sludge in the reactor.

Effect of initial phenol concentration :

From various batch experiments (having initial concentration 100 ppm to 500 ppm) it was observed that phenol conversion strongly depends on initial phenol concentration and optimum condition was arrived at 100 ppm (Fig. 6) concentration keeping the other parameters constant. At higher concentration of phenol, number of moles phenol increases compared to hydroxyl radical generated *in situ*. This may promote undesired side reactions instead of breaking aromatic ring. Experiments also revealed that color conversion was not up to the mark at higher phenol concentration. This is due to low rate of mass transfer.

Fig. 5. Optimization of catalyst concentration for phenol concentration.

Fig. 5A. Variation of iron concentration with Fenton's oxidation.

Fig. 6. Effect of initial phenol concentration on % conversion of phenol.

Relation between TOC removal and color transformation :

TOC removal gradually decreases with increasing contaminant concentration from 100 ppm to 500 ppm. Phenol conversion is not directly reflected in the TOC re-

moval efficiency. At optimum pH, catalyst concentration, oxidant dose and feeding mode the overall mineralization was merely 36.23% (Fig. 7) where phenol conversion was almost 98.32% (Table 2).

This is due to the fact that as the concentration of

Fig. 7. Relation between phenol conversion with TOC removal.

Table 2

Reaction condition	Initial phenol concentration (mg/L)	TOC removal after 30 min (%)
pH ~ 3.0	100	36.23
Catalyst concn : 0.42 mM	150	35.41
Phenol : H ₂ O ₂ = 1 : 12	250	33.80
Reaction volume = 100 L	500	17.87
Temperature = Ambient		

phenol decreases quickly, degraded products, such as maleic acid, catechol, hydroquinone and some unknown compounds appear. However, by the end of the reaction, only catechol and hydroquinone completely disappear. Several other compounds are still present in the solution in small amounts. The iron-organic complex is observed from the beginning of the reaction. Also, under these conditions, quinhydrone (a 1 : 1 complex of benzoquinone and hydroquinone) begins to appear, but quantification is not possible as it rapidly decomposes into its constituent molecules¹³.

It has been observed from experiment that once the dark brown color has been formed after 10–15 min, the TOC removal not reaches maximum value. Instead after 30 min when the dark color fades mineralization shows its maximum value.

IR study :

IR study report of the final solution has a strong cor-

relation with proposed mechanism. The O–H stretch of a carboxylic acid shows up from 3300–2500 as a characteristic wide, low band, sometimes with a small blip near the center. Another important for the carbonyl stretch of a carboxylic acid : an intense band from 1760–1690. The C–O stretch appears in the region 1320–1210. Presence of aliphatic carboxylic acid (may be maleic, acetic, formic, oxalic) clearly reveals the reason of unsatisfactory total organic carbon.

Reaction kinetics :

From the experimental Table it has been found that initial phenol degradation generally follow first order reaction kinetics w.r.t phenol concentration. The corresponding equation is :

$$\ln \left(\frac{[\text{phenol}]_t}{[\text{phenol}]_0} \right) = k_{\text{obs}} t \quad (6)$$

where k_{obs} represents the pseudo-first order rate constant.

From experimental runs it has been observed that a plot of $\ln ([\text{phenol}]_t/[\text{phenol}]_0)$ versus time in every experiment must lead to a straight line whose slope is k_{obs} . In Fig. 8 the linear straight line fitting was shown for three experiments having different initial phenol concentration, other parameters being constant. In one case deviation observed due to reason that after 30 min some reactant molecule formed and reaction no longer follow exact first order kinetics. It is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Curve fitting for first order kinetics.

The k_{obs} values were calculated from experimental data covering 90–98% removal of phenol at optimum pH. All these results support the pseudo-first order kinetics. Phenol degradation rates (R_D) were calculated by eq. (7),

$$R_D = - \frac{d [\text{phenol}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{phenol}]_0 \quad (7)$$

k_{obs} represents pseudo-first order rate constant which include concentration terms of Fe^{2+} , H_2O_2 .

The order of the phenol found out by this method is ≈ 0.902 .

The overall kinetic rate equation is

$$\frac{d [\text{phenol}]}{dt} = -k [\text{phenol}]$$

where k is the initial rate constant. The average rate constant for the concerned equation : $1.121 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Hence, the final rate equations become :

$$\frac{d [\text{phenol}]}{dt} = -1.121 \times 10^{-3} [\text{phenol}]^{0.902}$$

Color generation and phenol transformation also possess a strong similarity with the kinetic formulation.

Conclusion :

The present study was conducted in a large scale reactor which clearly predicts the applicability of this technology in industrial purpose. It is surely a cost effective and operator friendly technology. A strong relationship among color transformation, proposed mechanism and phenol conversion reveal the fact that using this technology as an effective pretreatment to conventional biological treatment system should be fruitful. Color change may be good physical indicator of the monitoring process. In future study emphasize will be given on betterment of the operational parameter so that the process can be effective for waste water having higher organic load.

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